

Human Participant Data Management Essentials

When working with human participants, the data may include information that identifies individuals directly or indirectly. Such data should be handled with special care throughout collection, storage, use, and sharing.

Personal data or sensitive data?

While personal data and sensitive data are related, under [GDPR](#) they have specific definitions that need to be taken into account during data collection, data handling, and data processing.

Personal data : encompasses data that can identify a person

- Names
- Contact details
 - Email, phone number
- Date of birth
- Home address
- Insurance number

Sensitive data: GDPR classifies these eight categories as particularly sensitive

- Racial and/or ethnic origin
- Belief system (religious or philosophical)
- Trade union membership
- Political affiliations
- Sexual orientation
- Genetic data
- Health data
- Biometric data

REMEMBER

All sensitive data is personal data ...

BUT

... not all personal data is sensitive data

C.A.R.E. Principles

C.A.R.E principles put participants, and their autonomy, at the centre of conversation for the governance of data within research.

While these principles were originally developed to address the power imbalance between indigenous communities and how research data about their communities was collected and used, the principles are beneficial to keep in mind when working with any community of human participants.

- **C**ollective benefit
 - Focuses on data benefiting the group
- **A**uthority to control
 - Focuses on data governance
- **R**esponsibility
 - Focuses on the researchers duty to the group
- **E**thics
 - Focuses on placing the groups rights at the centre of the data life cycle

Anonymisation and pseudonymisation

While these two concepts are related, they are not interchangeable. Both are ways to handle human data, yet are different processes with differing results to the privacy of the participants.

Pseudonymisation

The act of manually replacing identifiers with another value that stops the individual from being identified without additional context.

- Identifiers are replaced with a consistent code
- Re-identification is possible with additional information
- Datasets are still considered to be personal data

Anonymisation

A process where datasets are treated in a way that makes it impossible to identify individuals.

Usually done via a tool, such as [Amnesia](#).

- Identifiers are removed permanently
- Re-identification is not possible
- Datasets are no longer considered to be personal data
 - In this case, GDPR no longer applies

!! Pseudonymisation is reversible, so the right to withdrawal remains for participants. Anonymisation removes the right to withdrawal, as the process is irreversible. !!
For more information about the distinction, check out the [Data Protection Commission](#).

Best Practices

Careful day-to-day handling is as important as data storage and sharing.

- Participant consent
 - Gain consent before collecting any data
 - Ensure your [participant consent form](#) explains clearly what is being collected and why, as well as including details on participant withdrawal rights
 - Ensure your consent form allows you to publish and share your findings and data in a safe and appropriate way
- Data minimisation: Avoid collecting unnecessary identifiers from participants
 - No 'just in case' data items
- Do you need to conduct a [DPIA \(Data Protection Impact Assessment\)](#)?
- Avoid unnecessary copying, downloading, or transferring of the data
- Remove unnecessary personal identifiers as early as possible
 - Pseudonymise or anonymise data
- Store data securely on approved services and limit access to the necessary team only
- Be aware of the [TU Dublin Data Breach Procedures](#)